

Prometheus: Harnessing Fuzzy Logic and Natural Language for Human-centric Explainable Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract—Prometheus is an interpretable model which is suitable for the generation of visual and textual explanations grounded in common sense knowledge. This model can be seen as a special case of generalized additive models, which can be also interpreted as a list of (fuzzy) rules. The goodness of the model is illustrated with one benchmark dataset from the medical domain. Reported results are encouraging. They suggest that Prometheus exhibits a good balance between understandability and classification performance in comparison with other well-known models (e.g., linear models, decision trees or fuzzy rule-based classifiers) which are deemed as interpretable.

Index Terms—Explainable Artificial Intelligence, Interpretable Machine Learning, Shapley Values, Generalized Additive Models, Fuzzy Rule-based Classifiers

I. INTRODUCTION

In Greek mythology, Prometheus was a semi-god who stole a spark of fire from the gods and created humanity from clay [1]. Moreover, he is said to have brought fire (intelligence) to humankind. In this paper, we introduce a new Artificial Intelligence (AI) modelling method whose name takes inspiration from this myth, in that it constitutes a step ahead towards the creation of self-explaining AI models in real-world applications.

Given a classification or regression task, the objective of machine learning has been to mathematically formalise algorithms for maximising some accuracy measure for the given data. A wide variety of models have been created, some of them achieving impressive performance on benchmarking datasets. However, there is a class of problems for which having good performance metrics is not enough. In particular, a system that supports decision-making for fault-critical situations, or where someone has to take responsibility for the action, has limited utility if it does not provide any meaningful insight into its reasoning process. For example, if an advanced AI in a hospital suggests a diagnosis and a cure, the well-being of the patient is ultimately the responsibility of the doctor in charge and he/she is the person who in the end will have the final word about the diagnosis and treatment. Thus a doctor is going to use such an AI-based diagnostic system only if its recommendations are transparently explained, allowing

the professional to evaluate their soundness and possibly communicate them to the patient.

It is within this frame of responsibility, trust, fairness, accountability and liability that eXplainable AI (XAI) plays a key role [2]. An AI system that can explain its reasoning is more likely to inspire trust in decision-makers. Recently, XAI has received lots of attention, with proposals for different approaches and tools aimed to answer different questions. In this context, if we want to lower the barrier to access to these tools, then the use of the verbal modality and textual generation can sparkle an interactive communication between humans and AI that will help understandability and the transfer of knowledge [3]–[5]. This is because humans tend to vastly favour the modality of language when explaining their decisions and the reason behind them.

In this paper, we introduce Prometheus, an interpretable-by-design AI model that supports both visual explanations and textual descriptions of its reasoning. We have evaluated Prometheus with the Breast Cancer benchmark dataset [6]. Moreover, we have shown how Prometheus works in comparison with alternative methods in an illustrative example. The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows. Section II introduces related work. Section III describes how to build and interpret Prometheus XAI models. Section IV presents our experimental settings and reports achieved results. Section V concludes the paper and points out future work.

II. RELATED WORK

One important feature that distinguishes between different XAI approaches [7] is whether an explanation is generated after the prediction is done (post-hoc), or whether one tries to design an interpretable model in the first place.

A. Interpretable by design models

In the literature we find three broad classes of interpretable models; several variations exist within each class.

- **Rule-based Systems (RBSs):** a list of rules in the form IF X THEN Y. The more rules there are, the harder it becomes to understand the model.

- **Decision Trees (DTs)**: a list of rules nested into a tree structure. At each step of the reasoning process, the model is looking at just one “test” at a time and based on the result decides which branch to descend along the tree until it reaches a leaf that corresponds to the prediction.
- **Generalized Additive Models (GAMs)**: a class of models that are only concerned with first-order interactions between the features and the target. This allows the study of the effect of each feature one at a time.

Both RBSs and DTs are relatively easy to interpret and describe in natural language [8], [9]. However, as far as we know, it is rare to find linguistic explanations associated with GAMs (see e.g., [10]). GAMs are models of the form $g(y) = \sum_i f_i(x_i)$ where x_i represents the i -th feature of \mathbf{x} and $g(\cdot)$ is the *link function* (e.g., logistic sigmoid for classification tasks). Each f_i is called a *shape function* [11]. GAMs are interpretable due to the additive nature of the modelling, allowing a user to focus on the contribution of each feature without accounting for interaction effects. In other words, they are a class of models for which partial dependency plots and their generalisation, Individual Conditional Expectations [12], can be computed exactly, they let users follow the process of computation in a sequential manner, and they are not subject to variation effects (because interactions are restricted to first-order, by design, but see below for details on GA2Ms which incorporate interaction terms). The main types of GAM are:

- **Linear Models (LMs)**: where $f_i(x) = \beta_i$ and β_i is a static coefficient.
- **Scoring Systems**: similar to LMs, but where β coefficients are discrete and small [13].
- **Spline Systems**: each partial f_i is estimated with a spline.
- **GA2M**: introduces additional terms that explicitly deal with second-order interactions $f_i(x_j, x_k)$ which are described by heatmaps [14].
- **Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM)**¹: combines small trees and also deals with second-order interactions.
- **GAMs with Neural Networks**: each f_i is estimated with a neural network. They were first proposed by [15].

B. Post-hoc explanations

With black-box models, it is possible to some extent to generate post-hoc explanations of their behaviour, using different techniques. For example, LIME [16] makes a linear approximation to the black-box so that it is locally equivalent. On the other hand, SHAP [17] is inspired by the game-theoretic Shapley Values that assign to the feature x_j a contribution $\phi_j(x_j)$ such that

$$f(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}_x}[f(\mathbf{x})] = \sum_i \phi_i(x_i)$$

SHAP is in general NP-hard to compute, but for some models (like tree ensembles [18]) can be computed efficiently. Moreover, it is accessible and usable thanks to its open-source implementation.²

¹ Available at <https://github.com/interpretml/interpret>

² Available at <https://github.com/slundberg/shap>

The interpretation of these methods must nonetheless be conducted carefully as they have been shown to be potentially vulnerable to some adversarial attacks [19].

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROMETHEUS XAI MODEL

The architecture of Prometheus is depicted in Fig. 1. This is another step toward a human-centric approach to knowledge discovery and human-machine interaction. The user can benefit from flexibility in the customisation of the processing of data according to common-sense expert knowledge. Also, he/she can exploit the insights learnt from the model communicated with visualisations and textual explanations.

The first component of Prometheus is a *discretiser* that discretises continuous variables into k -bins (using a k -means or quantiles strategy) transforming the original instance into a wider vector of 0s and 1s (this can be interpreted as a way of building rules IF x_i IS IN BIN j). Each bin has a semantic meaning that can be linguistically refined by an expert, just by tuning the associated strong fuzzy partition. As an example let's imagine the task of recommending a certain movie to someone given that we have a feature that represents their age: the discretiser would produce a tuple of features stating whether age is *low*, *medium* or *high*. This initial partition can be semantically refined later by the user with personalized labels like *young*, *mid-age* or *old*.

The output of the discretiser is then combined linearly by an LM with zero bias (regularised by an L1 penalty as it incentives a sparse representation)³. In this way, a partial score is attributed to each partition and the final prediction (in log-odds space) will be the global aggregation (sum) of the fired partial scores. Going back to our example, a *young* person could contribute with a score of +1.2 (thus representing evidence of the class “Do recommend”) while an *old* one could contribute with -1.1 (thus being counter-evidence for the class, thus “Do not recommend”). If the *mid-age* contributes with 0, then it can be omitted for the sake of reducing the cognitive load to the user.

The generated model can be seen both as a GAM where each f_i is piece-wise constant, and as a fuzzy rule list aggregated by the sum operator (e.g., “ R_i : IF *feature* _{i} is *label* _{3} THEN *output* _{1} with $w = s$ ”). This means that we can use the visualisations typically used for GAMs but also the linguistic explanations associated with fuzzy rule-based systems. In particular, the interpretation of the model as a rule list can support the generation of simple linguistic explanations. This can be achieved for example by ad-hoc mapping rules to templates of the form “Instance i has a high value of feature f and this contributes s to the total log-odd score of class C .” Naturally, the language generated could also be tailored to the user, or made more or less precise depending on the context. Thus, we can produce a textual description of the process that leads to the final prediction.

We adopt a relatively simple generation strategy for textual descriptions in the present work, noting that more sophisticated

³The number of bins and the coefficient for regularisation are automatically chosen with cross-validation on the training data.

Fig. 1. A pictorial description of the proposed architecture.

methods have been developed in the field of Natural Language Generation [20]. Here, the textual generation process follows a template-based approach. Contributions are first divided into evidence and counter-evidence for the target class. They are then presented in an ordered way sorted by the absolute magnitude of their partial score so that more important features are presented first (see an illustrative example in Fig. 4, which will be described in depth in the next section). Then, the discretiser component gives us the option of using semantic labels to give a qualitative description of the magnitude of the feature. For example, if a feature had three bins (like in Fig. 1) we could establish that *for that particular feature* we assign one semantic label out of [*low, medium, high*]; with the meaning of this semantic label tied to the distribution of data. However, a given explanation can be excessively long due to many features contributing very little to the overall score. Accordingly, to keep the explanation shorter and relevant for the user, we have implemented a compression algorithm that groups small partial scores into a score called “other reasons”. The values are sorted by absolute value and then are progressively accumulated, until a threshold is met (while ensuring that the absolute magnitude of the resulting aggregation is smaller than the smallest remained partial score). The rate of

compression can be set by the user, allowing the user to focus first on what is most relevant and then giving him/her the option of delving into the details if needed.

It is important to note that even though the additive nature of the Prometheus model might qualitatively resemble SHAP, it is significantly different from it. This is because additive coefficients in Prometheus constitute in themselves the interpretable model. By contrast, SHAP provides these coefficients as a post-hoc explanation. Moreover Shapley values describe $f(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}_x}[f(\mathbf{x})]$ while for Prometheus they describe precisely $f(\mathbf{x})$. It is nonetheless possible to make use of the visualisation toolbox provided by the SHAP package (while keeping in mind that we are visualising something radically different).

IV. EXPERIMENTS

We have empirically assessed both the accuracy and complexity (as a proxy for explainability) of the Prometheus XAI model. As humans we have a limited cognitive capacity, thus between two systems of equal performances we would tend to find more interpretable a simple one. We considered the Breast Cancer dataset (taken from the UCI machine learning data repository [21]). This is a relatively small dataset (569 instances, 30 features) where explainability, as is expected in

medical diagnosis, is an important concern. All features are numerical and there are no missing values. The task consists of predicting if a given cancer is benign (357 instances) or malignant (212 instances) [6].

For comparison purposes, in addition to Prometheus, the following models are generated⁴: (i) EBMs; (ii) LM-L1 (with L1 regularisation chosen with 4-fold cross-validation); (iii) J48 decision tree; (iv) REPTree; (v) RandomTree; (vi) Fuzzy Hoeffding Decision Tree (FHDT) (vii) Fuzzy Unordered Rule Induction Algorithm (FURIA); and (viii) Random Forest (RF).

Figures 2 and 3 show the interpretability-accuracy trade-off of models which are deemed as interpretable⁵. Every measure is estimated with stratified 10-fold cross-validation. Classification performance is measured in terms of the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC AUC) in Fig. 2. Classification performance is measured in terms of F1 Score in Fig. 3. In both cases, the structural complexity of models is computed as the total rule length (TRL)⁶. In these figures, Prometheus emerges as the most accurate model, at the cost of higher structural complexity. Moreover, it performs reasonably well (ROC AUC = 0.988; F1 Score = 0.949) compared to the black-box model RF (ROC AUC = 0.991; F1 Score = 0.968). However, EBM (ROC AUC = 0.992; F1 Score = 0.971) achieves even better performance, which can be attributed to its higher flexibility due to the high number of shallow trees, which allow the modelling of a more complex shape function, and to the capability of modelling higher-order interactions. In addition, this high performance comes at the cost of increased model complexity (TRL=7680), i.e., the user has to deal with a more complex shape function representation for inspecting the model, what in practice jeopardizes intelligibility.

Regarding explainability, the prediction of a single instance consists of the summation of partial scores activated when a feature lies in a certain bin. This can be displayed in different ways (see Fig. 4). For example, the list of activated rules is given on top, a waterfall plot is given in the centre, and a linguistic explanation is given at the bottom. In addition, Fig. 5 shows the same example with a higher compression rate, i.e., with a less detailed and rougher explanation.

On the other hand, Figs. 6, 7, and 8 show the Shapely values associated with models LM-L1, RF, and EBM, respectively. These graphs provide similar information to that given by Prometheus: the final output is laid down as a sum of terms. The main difference is that this sum of terms amounts to the difference between the expected value of the function and the specific value of the instance in SHAP, while the sum directly

⁴We use the implementation of EBMs and LM-L1 in Python InterpretML and scikit-learn packages, respectively. We use the implementation of J48, REPTree, RandomTree, FHDT, FURIA and RF in ExpliClas [8], [9].

⁵EBM is not included in the figures because it uses a discretiser with 128 bins what yields huge structural complexity (TRL=7680) and makes impossible any linguistic interpretation of the model.

⁶TRL counts the number of premises and conclusions in a rule list like the one provided by FURIA or FHDT; TRL counts the number of nodes in a tree (like J48, REPTree or RandomTree); TRL counts the number of non-zero coefficients multiplied by 2 in an LM; TRL equals 2 x number of bins x number of features in Prometheus and EBM.

Fig. 2. The trade-off between classification performance (ROC AUC) and complexity (TRL); computed using stratified 10-fold cross-validation.

Fig. 3. The trade-off between classification performance (F1 Score) and complexity (TRL); computed using stratified 10-fold cross-validation.

explains the $f(x)$ in Prometheus. Moreover, it is important to notice how SHAP is a post-hoc method, thus it does not directly reflect the underlying computation. The explanation of Prometheus is instead exactly the description of its internal rationale. The explanations given by these different models show some inconsistencies, and this can be misleading and jeopardise user confidence. For example, *worst perimeter* is

Fig. 4. A full local factual explanation provided by Prometheus.

Fig. 5. Illustrative example of compressed explanation.

evidence for *benign* in case of LM-L1 but it is for *malign* in case of RF and EBM. Moreover, this feature is not highlighted among the most relevant ones by Prometheus.

In addition, the linguistic explanations provided by Prometheus can be compared to those given by ExpliClas:

- **J48:** *Diagnosis is malignant because mean concavity and worst area are medium.*
- **REPTree:** *Diagnosis is malignant because worst perimeter is medium.*
- **RandomTree:** *Diagnosis is malignant because mean area, mean smoothness, area error and worst concavity are medium.*
- **FHDT:** We have a high confidence in the classification result. It is very likely that diagnosis is *malign*. There is also a medium chance that it is *benign*. On balance *malign* is more likely, because in accordance with rule 7 *concavity error* is *low* and *worst concave points* is *high*.
- **FURIA:** We have a high confidence in the classification

Fig. 6. Local explanation given by SHAP for LM-L1 model.

Fig. 7. Local explanation given by SHAP for RF model.

result. It is very likely that diagnosis is *malign* because *worst concave points* is *high* and *worst radius* is *medium*.

As we can see above, different models are supported by different rationale and provide consistent but different complementary explanations. In the case of fuzzy classifiers (FHDT and FURIA), ExpliClas begins explanations with a sentence related to the confidence in the classification result which emerges from the rule firing degree associated with the winner rule. This is similar to how Prometheus begins each textual explanation (see Fig. 5) with a sentence verbalising the probability associated with the given classification.

ExpliClas also provides users with factual explanations of the inferred class but nothing is said about alternative classes. This is because explanations verbalise the information contained in the activated branch of a tree or the winner rule in a fuzzy classifier. On the contrary, Prometheus provides users with contrastive explanations, which verbalise which features are evidence for and against the inferred class.

Another commonality shared by ExpliClas and Prometheus is that they provide users with a graphical output along with the list of related rules. In the case of the illustrative example under consideration, FURIA fires rules:

Fig. 8. Local explanation given by SHAP for EBM model.

- R1: IF *worst radius* in [16.25, 16.82, inf, inf] and *worst concave points* in [0.1452, 0.1456, inf, inf] THEN *Diagnosis is malign* with CF = 0.99
- R2: IF *worst area* in [947.9, 967, inf, inf] and *worst fractal dimension* in [0.06469, 0.06515, inf, inf] THEN *Diagnosis is malign* with CF = 0.99

However, FURIA rules are not easily verbalised, so they need to be linguistically approximated by ExpliClas as:

- R1: IF *worst radius* is *medium* and *worst concave points* is *high* THEN *Diagnosis is malign*
- R2: IF *worst area* is *medium* and *worst fractal dimension* is *medium* THEN *Diagnosis is malign*

In the case of ExpliClas, explanations only pay attention to the winner rule (R1 in this example; because the two rules are activated with the same degree and then the first rule is selected). On the contrary, all listed rules contribute to the explanation elaborated by Prometheus.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have introduced Prometheus, an interpretable model that can produce both textual and visual explanations related to tabular data. This model can be seen as a weighted RBS with sum aggregation at inference level. We measured reasonable performances on classification metrics, beating LMs and DTs. In addition, the model compares favourably to RFs and EBMs, though its accuracy is slightly lower. Prometheus was designed for supporting linguistic explanations with different degrees of details. As future work, we plan exhaustive experimentation with more benchmark datasets. In addition, we plan to explore more sophisticated natural language generation techniques, multiclass classification and measuring the impact of explainability with intrinsic and extrinsic human evaluation. For the sake of reproducibility, Prometheus (as well as other related XAI tools) is available at <https://gitlab.citius.usc.es/jose.alonso/xai>.

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